

Preparing the Research & Innovation Core for Mission Ocean, Seas & Waters

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Report on virtual space pilot and website including overview of existing Mission contributions and spaces for Mission-related events

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0.2	7 December 2023	Prep4Blue Coordination Team	Comments
1.0	19 December 2023	Jan-Stefan Fritz (KDM)	Final version (to submit)

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Executive Summary

This executive summary provides an overview of the development and progress of the missionoceanwaters.eu website (Prep4Blue Task 2.3-Subtask 2.3.2), a key component in realizing PREP4BLUE's contribution to community building under the *EU Mission Restore our Ocean and Waters by 2030*.

Following much work a successful website has been launched at missionoceanwaters.eu.

The narrative guiding the website is structured around three levels: My Mission, Our Mission, and EU Mission, reinforcing a sense of community engagement and shared goals. The website features the Mission Lighthouses represented by interactive scenes showcasing individual and collective efforts. KDM, in collaboration with KUBIKFOTO GmbH, created distinctive and interactive "Kubikfoto" webpages to enhance user engagement. The website's structural overview is provided in Figure 3, with additional details in Annex 2.

Results from the website development include a draft presented at the Prep4Blue Annual General Meeting in 2023, incorporating participant feedback documented in Annex 1. Subsequently, a revised draft of the website was completed in mid-November 2023, and next steps include completing website content design and structure, translation, and filming specific sub-pages at scheduled events in April and May 2024. An official launch event is planned, ideally coinciding with established events like the European Maritime Day or a Mission Forum.

The interactive website effectively communicates the Mission's complexity and dynamism, but faces challenges in adjusting due to the inherent nature of websites. Multilingualism emerged as a particular challenge, requiring custom-developed solutions for translation due to the varied language preferences of speakers. Designing and constructing the website proved more complex than anticipated, with ongoing efforts to perfect it likely lasting until the end of the Prep4Blue project.

In summary, the missionoceanwaters.eu website offers a unique and important contribution to fostering community engagement and advancing the *EU Mission Restore our Ocean and Waters by 2030*, despite the challenges encountered in its development.

1 Introduction

This report covers WP2 Task 2.3 Subtasks 2.3.1., 2.3.2. and 2.3.3.. In the Grant Agreement, WP2 is described as follows:

WP2 focuses on developing a common narrative for the Mission and its contributors. The Mission will encompass hundreds of contributions from different communities across Europe and its implementation will require a number of institutions, platforms, and processes; some will be physical entities while others will be conceptual and abstract - for example, Lighthouses, citizen assemblies, Blue Parks, national hubs, etc. WP2 will deliver communication assets and tools as part of an overarching Communication Strategy for use by Mission initiatives.

It will also develop and pilot visionary virtual and physical Mission communication spaces for future Mission efforts. The aim is to build on and connect the many existing projects and initiatives at EU, national, and local levels, as well as inspire awe and wonder around the ocean - connecting people with things they deeply value and welcome - and eliciting interest in taking action.

T2.3 will pilot the narrative and Communications Strategy through a social media campaign, virtual spaces, and intergenerational and inclusive physical spaces as venues for meetings, interactions, exhibitions, etc., to engage Mission contributors and citizens across Europe. The task will organise at least two exhibitions/public events in iconic spaces (e.g., Ocean Space | Venice) with artists, designers, architects, the European Bauhaus, and other initiatives to showcase the Mission and its contributors. These products will be positioned as globally-visible contributions to the UN Ocean Decade.

Subtask 2.3.1: Pilot a social media campaign, including public competitions, aimed at bringing Mission information to young people. The Terms of Reference will be part of the Communication Strategy. This task will draw on and coordinate with T3.4 and other campaigns across Europe to engage citizens.

Subtask 2.3.2: Conceptualize, design, and pilot an interactive, multidimensional virtual Mission space (website), including an overview of all Mission contributions and Mission-related events. During the coronavirus pandemic, online venue technology has increased dramatically. This task will include working with online venue developers to explore the most advanced, open-source, accessible (CMS) software available and develop a virtual space pilot. This space will include a lobby, information booth, several auditoriums, cinema, exhibition hall, social media wall, etc., and ideally serve as a model, or the actual website, for the duration of the Mission. Working with WP4 WP6 and others, this task will showcase progress in Mission implementation (e.g., a Progress Dashboard and Map), including, where possible, increased restoration efforts and their impact on communities. It is intended be used by both the public and mission community with public and private (log-in) spaces featuring tools and information to aid both. We will work with other EU Missions (e.g., cities), living labs, citizen initiatives, etc. in order ensure inclusivity.

Subtask 2.3.3: Conceptualise, design, and pilot with potential venues (e.g., museums and aquaria) from around the world physical Mission spaces that serve to exhibit Mission contributions and as venues to hold Mission-related activities (e.g., citizen assemblies, foresight workshops, future labs, etc.) in Europe. The budget for implementing this subtask will be allocated when the Terms of Reference have been finalized. A close cooperation/co-location with WP3 is foreseen.

This report focuses on accomplishments and next Deliverable will focus on an mid-term analysis (D2.4) to help us to make adjustments before a final analysis and recommendations are produced at the end of the project (D2.5).

2 Methods

Methodologically, the emphasis in WP 2 has been on narrative development. The narrative employed in the missionoceanwaters.eu website, was developed in Deliverable D2.1., entitled *Narrative Guide for Mission Restore our Ocean and Waters by 2030*. The basic narrative is structured around three levels of activity, which are key to implementing the *EU Mission Restore our Ocean and Waters by 2030*: My Mission, Our Mission and EU Mission (see Figure 1). The intent is to reinforce the sense that individuals are part of a community that is striving to achieve certain aims, in this case the EU Mission Ocean and Waters' goals.

These levels were articulated following an extensive consultation phase and based on the agreed texts underpinning the *EU Mission Restore our Ocean and Waters by 2030* (Figure 2). They are now the foundations of the missionoceanwaters.eu website.

The Website Structure

As illustrated in Figure 3 below, each one of the Lighthouses is represented by a “scene” intended to showcase the Lighthouse and contributing individuals and activities. These scenes employ descriptive and viewpoint narratives with the aim to “emotionalize” the Mission through interactive elements which involve the user and are meant to be fun. The user is immersed by interacting with people, their surroundings, products, and objects thereby experiencing first-hand the Mission lighthouses and actions to implement their goals.

KDM has worked with a private service partner, KUBIKFOTO GmbH, to produce the website and the distinctive, interactive “Kubikfoto” webpages. KUBIKFOTO was chosen after an extensive search process for their award-winning, ocean-related website designs, for example, for [Greenpeace](#).

Annex 1 provides a more detailed overview of the missionoceanwaters.eu website in hierarchical form.

Figure 3 provides a structural overview of the missionoceanwaters.eu website.

Filming the scenes took place in conjunction with Mission events in:

- The Atlantic/Arctic Lighthouse scene was filmed in Ballycotton near Cork, Ireland (November 2022)
- The Baltic/North Sea Lighthouse scene and Plastic Pirates were filmed in Hamburg, Germany (April 2023), and
- Mediterranean Lighthouse scene was filmed in Palermo, Italy (May 2023).

Two further scenes are planned for Groningen, Netherlands (April 2024) on nature restoration and in Tulcea, Romania (May 2024) on the Danube/Black Sea Lighthouse (see more details below in section 3.3.)

Filming in conjunction with Mission events is fundamentally important to win as many contributors to the Mission as possible.

Over the course of one year almost 30 testimonials were filmed, many of which are now available on the website. Over the course of the coming 6 months another 10-20 testimonials will be filmed and embedded in the website. The website further references many dozen EU projects and initiatives contributing to the implementation of the Mission.

Events

WP2 has committed to contributing to community building at least two Mission-related events. By late 2023, WP2 had already contributed to a number of Mission events, focusing on developing and publishing social media content. In addition, the social media campaign Mobile Journalists (MOJOs) is being launched with four early-career ocean professionals developing content from all four Mission Lighthouses.

In line with WP2 commitment and with a view to events planned in 2024, the aim is to showcase the website and the work of the MOJOs at least at two events during the year. These events will be chosen with Commission officials and the PREP4BLUE Coordination Team.

3 Results

3.1 Result 1: Website Draft

A first draft of missionoceanwaters.eu was produced in summer 2023 and presented at the Prep4Blue Annual General Meeting. The responses of the participants are included in Annex 1. These comments were all incorporated into the website and a revised version was produced.

3.2 Result 2: Revised Draft

A revised draft was completed in mid November 2023, with improved language and navigation features.

3.3 Next Steps

The following next steps are foreseen to implementing and completing Prep4Blue Task 2.3-Subtask 2.3.2:

Step 1	December 2023	Complete the existing website contents design and structure.
Step 2	January 2024	Complete translation
Step 3	15-19 April 2024	Film Wadden Sea sub-page on the impacts of the REST-COAST and WaterLANDS projects at their joint meeting in Groningen, Netherlands.
Step 4	13-17 May 2024	Film Danube Lighthouse “Kubikfoto” page in conjunction with the Deltas and Wetlands Symposium in Tulcea, Romania.

Step 5	March - June 2024	Organize an official launch event, ideally in conjunction with an established event such as the European Maritime Day or a Mission Forum
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4 Conclusions

Designing and constructing this website was substantially more complicated than anticipated. This effort remains a work in progress that will be continued until the end of Prep4Blue.

Strength:	<p>An interactive website allows an otherwise complicated Mission, which encompasses 3 objectives and 4 Lighthouses as well as hundreds of contributions, to become meaningful and dynamic.</p> <p>The website now contains many dozens of contributions to the Mission. A detailed overview is available in Annex 2.</p>
Weakness:	<p>Websites are by nature difficult to adjust. Most changes require programming work, which is costly and time consuming.</p> <p>Filming and website production were delayed by a few months mainly due to the need to film in conjunction with Mission events as a source of testimonials.</p> <p>Production was delayed by a few weeks due to website reprogramming in order to make a complex website as easily navigable as possible. This weakness has been overcome.</p>
Challenge:	<p>Ensuring the complementarity of the variety of online Mission services: At present the European Commission and service providers have websites:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - A central website on the European Commission website - A Mission Ocean and Waters Service Platform - A map of Mission lighthouse contributions - A project dashboard <p>A challenge for the missionoceanwaters.eu website was to ensure complementarity and added-value.</p> <p>Multilingualism: The intent was to have all speakers speak in their native language and translate into English. In reality speakers mostly chose to or insisted on speaking English, with only a fragmented few speaking their native languages. With that, the translation in the various directions has become a very difficult task. A single software programme cannot do the task, so a mixture of programmes has been custom developed, and will be tested in late 2023.</p>

Opportunity:	<p>The aim is to make this website a public face of the Mission. The hope is that it will offer a glimpse into the exciting contributions that are being made to implement the EU <i>Mission Restore our Ocean and Waters by 2030</i>.</p> <p>By ensuring complementarity and added-value the goal of making this website a public face of the Mission can be achieved successfully.</p> <p>This would be ideally realized by embedding the website on the Mission homepage.</p>
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5 ANNEXES

5.1 Annex 1: Feedback from Project Partners

This annex contains original feedback from the 2023 Prep4Blue Annual Meeting in Venice. The feedback is in the original contribution as delivered verbally following a presentation and a testing session with the website.

General Comments:

- While many were impressed with the video/imagery, the hard truth is that it was difficult for many to navigate and use due to loading and browser issues. There is also missing content and spelling errors that really need to be corrected quickly as it's now live.
- All had problems with Safari, Chrome, and Firefox – only Edge seemed to work well. Load time is long
- Lots of content is missing.
- Information points are too small
- Need to explain closer to beginning different types of websites
- Links to PREP4BLUE pages for events and charter info
- Need social media icons
- Need translation
- Need images on connect page along with contact info
- It would be great if the voice reply to the questions is also written – not all uses websites with sound on.
- Information “i” does not work on firefox.
- Its difficult to figure out what the target audience is, is it ocean professionals, citizens, youth, all?
- There are a lot of references that only stakeholders involved with MO would know.
- It is not intuitive to know how to go from one page to another, through the initial swiping through the objectives.
- The swiping from right to left bad/good on the objectives is nice, but would work better if the sub-header is also shown while swiping, it was only by coincidence that I swiped all the way through so it showed.
- Translation of Mission Website
- At least in the 3 working languages of the Commission (EN, FR, DE)
- Not visible if translation is available Swipe on the pictures
- Swipe is more visible
- the pictures are really nice/good looking Section on the LH
- Not really visible that you can sitch from one place to another.
- The arrow is too small or not contrasted enough
- For the individual/people, their names and function look like a link, but it's not one
- Palermo section
- EU Mission graphic/logo not visible (or only half way)
- Interview of Inès
- We cannot pause or go fast forward

- On firefox, we cannot get the zoom in when we click on the bubbles (aka 'degraded sea' and 'protected seas')
- The website is very heavy, it causes delays in the recordings and causes people to click on multiple buttons to test out whether the page is responding, and this cuts recordings that are playing after 30 seconds or so.
- Some tabs are blank (eg. Danube) and some buttons unresponsive
- Scrolling down on the opening page does not work on my computer, so I had to click the small arrows steps on the bottom left, which I would not do if I had not known that there is more content further down
- The prosperous vs exploited dichotomy is strangely illustrated. Economic activity/blue economy is portrayed as inherently negative.
- Only other language than English seems to be German?
- Links to other mains sites, Europe.eu page in mission and later on MIP should perhaps be more prominently displayed?
- If the page is empty, it would be good to know (e.g. the classic “under construction”)
- Footer large with lot of empty space
- UX was good on my computer (CAD workstation), but Android Tablets might encounter performance problems
- On Edge sometimes the image were not loading (only after an explicit reload) [Mission Ocean \(missionoceanwaters.eu\)](http://MissionOcean(missionoceanwaters.eu))
- When asking a person on the connect pages, it comes only as a sound-playback, but not as text when muted (might be a problem for deaf people, in terms of *barrier-free access*)

Home Page:

- The text below the objectives is a bit small and sometimes hard to read because of the bright background; also, sometimes it's too long.
- It is not possible to scroll with the mouse, only using arrows.
- No link in the sentence; Find more information on the European Commission dedicated website.
- Tiles are a bit large (maybe an image is mission)
- Menu animation a little bit distracting when clicking on the

About:

- It jumps sections if you scroll down using arrows.
- Graphically a bit plain;
- Text too small;
- It could be useful to add graphics to explain the Missions;
The menu at the bottom page doesn't work;
- The link to the 'Find out more about the Missions' doesn't work if right clicked (if opened directly the page is empty - perhaps because there is no content yet?)

Explore:

- It's not clear how to select the locations;
- The Danube page doesn't have content yet.
- Text not readable sometimes because of the bright background

Connect:

- There is no link connected to emails.

Digital Academy

- images are cropped, video preview is very large

Annex 2: Missionoceanwaters.eu Sitemap

Main Pages	Sub-Pages	Fly-to-Pages	Info-Points	Info-Points - European Projects & Initiatives mentioned in text box	Testimonials & Statements on Fly-to-Pages	Other Info Boxes	Notes
Home page							
	Protected - Destroyed						Presents Mission Objective 1: Protect and restore marine and freshwater ecosystems and biodiversity
	Pristine - Polluted						Presents Mission Objective 2: Prevent and eliminate pollution
	Prosperous - Exploited						Presents Mission Objective 3: Make the sustainable blue economy carbon-neutral and circular
Lighthouse North & Baltic Sea			Baltic and North Sea Lighthouse				
			Climate and Weather Tourism	EU Climate-ADAPT			
			Early Career Scientists	Atlantic ECOP Programme			
				APECS			
				Global ECOP Programme			
		More about the Mission	Vegetables from the Sea	OLAMUR	Kestutis Sadauskas (COM), n.n. (DK), Andreas Reinhardt (DE), Lars Baumler (DE), Karen Wiltshire (DE), Katja Matthes (DE), n.n. (NO),		
			Emissions and Pollution	ULTFARMS			
		Plastic Pirates	More about Plastic Pirates				
		More about citizen science	Plastic Pollution in the Sea				
			Citizen Science	EU4OCEAN			
			Citizen science in action	EU-Citizen.Science Database			
		What tools do I need for citizen science?	Citizen Science	Cities-Health Toolkit			
				CoastSnap Spain			

Menu Pages	About						Describes the Mission in basic terms and provides links to further information
	Explore						
	Connect					Mission Ocean and Waters Help Desk	Connect Menu Page Info boxes present further resources available to interested parties to help them connect with the Mission and Mission partners
						The Mission on Social Media	
						Mission Light houses	
						Mission Ocean and Waters Digital Academy	
						Citizen science	
						Mission Events	
						Mission Charter	
						Mission Project Database	
	Academy						
	Imprint						